

ALEKSANDER FEINBERG IS A NATIONAL POET OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In Uzbekistan, Alexander Arkadievich Feinberg is recognised as the national poet. Alexander Feinberg is one of the most illustrious figures in Uzbekistan's poetry canon. His body of work is remarkably diverse. Thirteen poetry collections that he has written have been released in Tashkent, Moscow, and St. Petersburg. This article talks about his life and creative work.

Key words: talented poet, skillful translator, national poet.

In Uzbekistan, Alexander Arkadievich Feinberg is recognised as the national poet. Alexander Feinberg is one of the most illustrious figures in Uzbekistan's poetry canon. His body of work is remarkably diverse. Thirteen poetry collections that he has written have been released in Tashkent, Moscow, and St. Petersburg. Alexander Feinberg was named an honorary "People's Poet of Uzbekistan" in 2004 for his contributions to the advancement of literature. Four years later, he was given the Pushkin Medal, the State Award of the Russian Federation.

Alexsandr Feinberg, a talented translator, introduced Russian-speaking readers to numerous works by well-known Uzbek poets. The poem "The Uprising of the Immortals" by Erkin Vakhidov was successfully published in Moscow, while the poetry collections "Swan Flock" by Abdulla Aripov, Hosiyat Rustamova, Sirojiddin Sayyid, and Omon Matchon were published in Tashkent.

Alexander Feinberg has spread as an inimitable writer from Uzbek literature to world literature. Alexander came from a brunette family and was a blue-eyed, gorgeous young man. His family and hardships are well known to everyone. They can be a great motivation for people and are a worthy example for everyone. With the infinite grace and mercy off fate, the poet benefited from the friendliness and generosity of the Uzbek people, whose hearts are as warm as the sun and who are tolerant and kind. He would have passed away before his birth if his family had not encountered Uzbeks, as we were repeatedly told. Anastasia Alexandrovna Feinberg was born in Moscow in 1904, while her father Arkady Lvovich was born in Gatchins, close to Saint Petersburg, in 1891. What was called "mass repression" had not spared his parents from its atrocities. The exile in Siberia, which attracted a sizable population under Stalin's rule, is, in fact, what brought the author's parents together.

The poet's parents realised that the Feinberg surname was inappropriate for someone who was going to survive the German troops in World War II when they smelled Kolima in Novosibirsk. The three-year-old brother of the poet had two pieces of paper in his hat. First, it writes "Chisinau," whereas the second one writes "Tashkent." When the eldest son of the Feinberg family chose "Tashkent," the entire Feinberg family was saved. As a result, they reached Tashkent in 1937. The poet Alexander Arkadievich Feinberg, who wrote for both the Russian and Uzbek people, was born in Tashkent on November 2, 1939, two years later. The most formative years of his life, his childhood, fell during the horrific and perilous years of World War II. "The houses of Yelena Sergeevna Bulgakova, Anna Akhmatova, Faina Ranevskaya, and Vladimir Lugovsky; Alexei Tolstoy's yard; Tatyana Sergeevna, Yesenina's shelter... how many more lives were saved due to the conflict in Tashkent, my hometown at

the time, during those years, due to the conflict in those years?" Leaving out my parents, who arrived in 1937 and gave birth to me in 1939. These thoughts are a crystal-clear illustration of life's challenges and the procedures required in overcoming them.

You aren't holler, or a silent coward
And neither grumpy, nor that young
And neither slave, nor pimp or a punk
My foes! Your unity has a power

He's intertwined with that snooker pot
Where poems were in a crumpled paper
And fizzy wine was a dripping favor
A side dish watermelon starts to rot

Save me God from roses of this garden
Indeed I don't want you to burden
Expel them. I wish to be alone

He is the author of fifteen poem collections (including a two-volume posthumous book compiled by the author), and also four feature films and more than twenty animated films based on his scripts. He translated into Russian the poems of Alisher Navoi and many other modern Uzbek poets. Alexander Feinberg's poems were published in the local magazines like *Smena*, *Yunost*, *Novy Mir*, *Star of the East*, *Novaya Volga* and in periodicals of foreign countries: the USA, Canada and Israel. In addition to four feature films and over twenty animated films based on his scripts, he is the author of fifteen collections of poems, including a two-volume posthumous book. Along with many other contemporary Uzbek poets, he translated Alisher Navoi's poetry into Russian. The poetry of Alexander Feinberg were published in foreign publications such as those from the USA, Canada, and Israel, as well as in local magazines such as *Smena*, *Yunost*, *Novy Mir*, *Star of the East*, and *Novaya Volga*. In addition to writing the screenplays for eighteen animated films, he authored seven scripts for feature films, including "At the very blue sky," "House under the hot sun," and "Burned near Kandahar."

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